

INFLUENCE OF CO-CURRICULAR ACTIVITIES ON MENTAL HEALTH OF HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS

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Abstract: *The present study is intended to examine the influence of co-curricular activities on mental health of higher secondary students. The study was conducted using survey method. The study was conducted on a sample of 300 higher secondary students randomly selected from the various government and private schools of Kovilpatti Taluk. Tools for collecting the data included, Mental Health Scale for School Students constructed and standardized by the investigators (2018) and Co-curricular activity scale, a standardized questionnaire developed by Dr. T. Ranjith Kumar and Dr. R. Selvaraju (2014). The data were analyzed using Pearson Correlation Analysis and Regression analysis. The correlation analysis revealed that there is significant negative relationship between mental health and co-curricular activities of higher secondary students and also the regression analysis exposed that the variable “Co-curricular activities” is strongly influence the mental health of higher secondary students.*

IndexTerms – Mental Health, Co-curricular activities, Higher Secondary Students

I. INTRODUCTION

Every activity in school life plays a significant role in development of students. Co-curricular activities are an essential part of school life and helps in enhancing learning process of students at school. Co-Curricular activities are compulsory activities which is important for every student to participate. Co-curricular are designed and balanced with academic curriculum so that every student gets to learn beyond subjects. Co-curricular activities are meant to bring social skills, intellectual skills, moral values, personality progress and character appeal in students. It includes athletics, cultural events, Library activities, science lab activities, classroom activities, creative arts and meditation etc. Co-curricular activities require students to stay active at school by participation since, students have no option to skip these activities as it's a part of their curriculum. Students have to be a part of co-curricular activities like athletics, gymnastics, yoga, indoor games, and meditation etc. These activities are beneficial for students' physical fitness as well as mental health and they are relieved from academic stress[3]. Mental Health is not simply a state of happiness or contentment of outgoingness or accommodation to circumstances, although it may involve these characteristics. . Mental Health is the capacity of an individual to form harmonious adjustments to one's social and physical environment[2]. Aspects of attitudes toward self, growth and development, self-actualization Integration of Personality and mastery of the environment must be considerate in judging whether a person is mentally healthy or not. Ask virtually any teacher, school counselor or principal to describe the challenges that interfere with students ability to succeed in school, and high on the list will be increasing number of diagnosed and undiagnosed mental health disorders impacting students. This more than just a perception: Research indicates that substantial numbers of children and adolescents are experiencing mental health problems. The need of mental health support in schools has never been so great [1]. Co-curricular activities facilitate in the development of various domains of mind and personality such as intellectual development, emotional development, social development, moral development and aesthetic development. Creativity, Enthusiasm, and Energetic, Positive thinking are some of the facets of personality development and the outcomes of Extracurricular activities. For all-round development of the child, there is a need of emotional, physical, spiritual and moral development that is complemented and supplemented by Co-curricular Activities. Co-curricular activities are the true and practical experiences received by students. To a greater extent, the theoretical knowledge gets strengthened when a relevant co-curricular activity is organized related to the content taught in the classroom. Intellectual aspects of personality are solely accomplished by Classroom, while aesthetic development, character building, spiritual growth, physical growth, moral values, creativity, etc. are supported by co-curricular activities [5]. The benefits of co-curricular activities can improve a teenager's quality of life in several ways. They provide opportunities for community involvement, as well as a platform for developing mental resilience. A full and busy time-table requires responsibility and time management and there is now a growing body of research that is telling us that being 'active' and participating in co-curricular activities drastically reduces the probability of mental health issues. One of the greatest benefits of co-curricular activities is that they promote mental, emotional, and physical health. They require pupils to use strategy, manage time effectively, cooperate with others, develop new skills, be social, be confident etc. The list goes on. By engaging in co-curricular activities, pupils learn how to be productive members of society. This establishes self-esteem, self-worth, and allows them to see their potential. Pupils who do not participate in co-curricular activities are far more likely to experience anxiety, depression and social difficulties[4].

II. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

Methodology is the procedure or the technique used to conduct the research study. The survey method was found most appropriate for the study.

III. SAMPLE AND TOOLS USED

The study was conducted on a sample of 300 higher secondary students randomly selected from the various government and private schools of Kovilpatti Taluk. Tools for collecting the data included, Mental Health Scale for School Students

constructed and standardized by the investigators (2018) and Co-curricular activity scale, a standardized questionnaire developed by Dr. T. Ranjith Kumar and Dr. R. Selvaraju (2014).

IV. STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED

The investigator used Pearson Correlation Analysis and Regression analysis to analyze the collected data.

V. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To find out whether there is any significant relationship between mental health and co-curricular activities of higher secondary students.
- To find out whether there is any significant influence of co-curricular activities on mental health of higher secondary students.

VI. HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

- There is no significant relationship between mental health and co-curricular activities of higher secondary students.
- There is no significant influence of co-curricular activities on mental health of higher secondary students.

VII. ANALYSIS OF DATA

Correlation analysis

Null Hypothesis :1 There is no significant relationship between mental health and co-curricular activities of higher secondary students.

Table – 1 Pearson Product Moment Correlation test shows the relationship between mental health and co-curricular activities of higher secondary students

Variable	X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY	Calculated value	Remarks
Mental Health And Co-Curricular Activities	19289	28807	1254717	239159	77674	-0.232	S

(At 5% level of significance, for df 300, the table value of ' χ^2 ' is 0.088)

It is inferred from the above table that calculated 'r' value (-0.232) is greater than the table value (0.088) for df (300) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. It shows that there is significant negative relationship between mental health and co-curricular activities of higher secondary students.

Regression analysis

Null Hypothesis :2 There is no significant influence of co-curricular activities on mental health of higher secondary students.

Table – 2 Regression analysis showing the significant influence of co-curricular activities on mental health of higher secondary students

Predictors	B	SE	β	t	Sig.	R	R ²	R ² x 100 (% of Variance)	F	Sig.
Constant	121.45	3.682		32.98	.000	0.232	0.054	5.4	16.95	0.000**
Co-curricular activities	-0.702	0.171	-0.232	-4.117	.000					

** Significant at 1% level

From the Table-2 it is evident that the obtained 'F' value, 16.95 with degrees of freedom (1, 298) is greater than the table value 3.85 at 0.01 level of significance. This suggests that the predictor variable, co-curricular activities (X) is also significant in predicting mental health (Y). So the null hypothesis is rejected. It indicates that there is significant influence of co-curricular activities on mental health of higher secondary students. And also the β coefficients of the variable co-curricular activities in the development of the regression equation for mental health (Y) is 0.232. It is evident from the table that co-curricular activity is a significant predictor of mental health. The beta value 0.232 denotes that for every unit of mental health, co-curricular activities can predict 23.2%. And also the t-value for leadership traits is 32.98 which indicate that the variable "Co-curricular activities" is strongly influence the mental health of higher secondary students.

VIII. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- There is significant negative relationship between mental health and co-curricular activities of higher secondary students.
- There is significant influence of co-curricular activities on mental health of higher secondary students.

IX. CONCLUSION

From the above discussion and findings of the present investigation, come to the conclusion that the variable "Co-curricular activities" is strongly influence the mental health of higher secondary students. So the investigator suggested that the higher secondary schools may give more importance to co-curricular activities for ensuring the development of mental health of higher secondary students. Each and every year, the government may arrange the Comprehensive school mental health programs include mental health promotion and prevention programming for all students as well as screening, assessment, and effective prevention and treatment interventions and services for those students with more intensive needs.

X. REFERENCES

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